

p-fluorophenylalanine (FPA), and ethionine — on growth and differentiation of cultured explants (root, shoot, endosperm, and embryo) of indica rice varieties Sita and Rajendra Dhan 201. All the chemicals decreased the rate of elongation of roots and shoots differentiated from treated embryos and fresh and dry weights of root, shoot, and endosperm calli. The extent of growth inhibition depended on the chemical and its concentration. Of the three, ethionine was most effective.

The morphological changes induced by the chemicals were manifested at the macromolecular levels as well. They lowered the levels of DNA, protein, and carbohydrates of the plantlets differentiated from chemically treated embryos, thereby indicating an overall disturbance in general metabolism (see table).

The decrease in the amount of total DNA gives indirect evidence for the changes induced in the levels of ploidy

Effects of antimetabolites on DNA, protein, and carbohydrate contents of 10-day-old plantlets differentiated from excised embryos.

Chemical	Concentration (mg/liter)	Amount in µg/g fresh weight of plantlets		
		DNA	Protein	Carbohydrate
Control	0.0	1060.0 ±44.9	417.6 ±28.4	544.3 ±21.1
Chloral hydrate	82.7	534.2 ±31.4	198.0 ±28.3	259.6 ±21.8
	165.4	237.4 ±31.1	130.3 ±2.8	150.7 ±10.8
	827.0	204.6 ±52.6	113.2 ±14.2	141.5 ±3.0
FPA	25.0	973.0 ±25.9	273.9 ±17.8	228.6 ±13.1
	50.0	789.7 ±57.1	176.2 ±28.1	187.2 ±3.8
	100.0	463.2 ±55.8	141.7 ±20.4	149.7 ±6.7
Ethionine	5.0	735.6 ±69.4	311.9 ±16.5	345.6 ±25.2
	10.0	295.7 ±32.3	163.7 ±40.2	317.8 ±15.8
	15.0	253.0 ±8.8	129.4 ±16.2	296.6 ±2.3

of the treated tissues. Cytological studies of the treated tissues are needed to reveal the nature of permanent heritable

changes brought about by these antimetabolites. □

Yield potential

Performance of japonica/indica cross derivatives under rainfed upland conditions

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Pre-wet season rainfed rice is grown in about 336.4 thousand ha in northern West Bengal. Rainfall varies from 4,000 mm at Cooch-behar to 1,430 mm at Malda; 80% falls between May and Sep. Drought is not common in Cooch-behar, Jalpaiguri, and Darjeeling districts, but happens occasionally in West Dinajpur and Malda. Germination and initial growth of the crop direct seeded early Mar in the terai region of Jalpaiguri and Cooch-behar is affected by low temperature (17-20 °C). Growth of the crop seeded late Apr and

May in West Dinajpur and Malda is affected by high temperature (around 40 °C).

The problems associated with prekharif yields include unevenly occurring drought spells; soil deficiencies, mostly N and P; diseases,

mostly blast, sheath rot, and brown spot; insects, termites, stem borers, mealybug, and leafhoppers; and root-knot nematodes. Weeds also are an important problem.

We screened 37 F₄ bulk population crosses including japonicas and indicas from IRRI and local cultivars at Malda in prekharif 1986. Seeds were sown in

Table 1. Screening F₄ bulk crosses under rainfed upland conditions. Malda, India, 1986.

Designation	Cross	Varietal group ^a	Panicle length (cm)	Duration (d)	Fertile grains (no./panicle)	Grain fertility (%)	Selections made (no.)
IR47724-14	Moroberekan/IRAT177	VI/VI	16-25	90	50-140	12-47	5
IR47730-4	IRAT112/Apura	VI/I	15-23	81-92	42-92	0-60	23
IR47705-6	Moroberekan/Palawan	VI/VI	15-20	88-90	52-100	10-71	10
IR47697-2	ITA235/IR9669 sel.	VI/I	15-20	90-92	54-85	32-70	8
IR47688-35	IRAT112/Sein Talay	VI/I	15-22	90-91	79-102	45-50	3
IR47687-10	IRAT104/Salumpikit	VI/I	16-19	91-94	80-135	0-72	5
IR47699-28	IRAT104/Palawan	VI/VI	15-17	89	80-115	39-55	2
IR4768-33	IRAT104/Salumpikit	VI/I	13-18	91-93	46-68	37-38	2
IR47721-21	IRAT177/H.T. Boewani	VI/I	15-22	89	70-113	12-55	8
IR47701-20	ITA235/UPLRi 7	VI/I	17-21	80	78-94	63-65	2
IR47699-22	ITA235/Palawan	VI/VI	19-24	81-93	65-140	39-67	5
Dular	Local check		20	85	81	32	
Panke	Local check		23	100	123	9	
Soni	Local check		19	82	65	43	

^aI = indica, VI = japonica.

early May. Individual plant selection was based on maturity, panicle length, grains per panicle, grain fertility, and grain acceptability (Table 1). The bulk population materials were as early as local cultivars. Some of them showed better seed fertility and grain numbers per panicle than local cultivars. Duration was about 90 d. The most promising materials are japonica/japonica crosses — Moroberekan/IRAT177 and ITA235/ Palawan. Lack of rain (108 mm) during Aug 1986 affected the reproductive and maturing stages.

Selected plants were sown 3 Oct 1986 to test cold tolerance at the vegetative stage. The transplanted crop was

Table 2. Cold tolerance of selected advanced lines of rainfed upland crosses. Malda, India, 1986-87.

Designation	Cross	Varietal group	Lines tested (no.)	Survival (%)	Average cold score (0-9 scale)	Range of cold tolerance
IR47687-10	IRAT104/Salumpikit	VI/I	3	12.5	7.0	7-7
IR47698-32	IRAT112/Sein Talay	VI/I	1	87.5	4.0	3-5
IR47688-78	IRAT112/Sein Talay	VI/I	6	45.8	7.0	5-9
IR47697-2	ITA235/IR9669 sel.	VI/I	6	62.5	5.8	3-9
IR47699-22	ITA235/Palawan	VI/VI	3	12.5	6.0	4-9
IR47699-28	ITA235/Palawan	VI/VI	2	56.3	5.5	5-6
IR47701-20	ITA235/UPLRi-7	VI/I	3	43.8	8.0	7-9
IR47705-6	Moroberekan/Palawan	VI/VI	8	64.5	6.7	5-9
IR47721-21	IRAT177/H.T. Boewani	VI/I	6	52.5	4.7	1-9
IR47724-14	Moroberekan/IRAT177	VI/VI	3	33.8	6.6	6-7
IR47730-4	IRAT112/Apura	VI/I	5	12.5	6.5	6-7
Soni	Local check			25.0	9.0	8-9
Dular	Local check			12.5	9.0	9-9

screened 3 Jan 1987. Average minimum temperatures were 18 °C in Nov and

13 °C in Dec. Table 2 shows crosses promising for survival percentage. □

Japonica and indica differences in large vascular bundles in culm

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We studied the number of large vascular bundles in the first internode from the

top (NLVBFI) and the number of primary branches of panicle (NPBP) at heading, in 45 indica (hsien) and japonica (keng) type varieties during 1981-82. NLVBFI was 20.9 ± 6.3 for indica type and 10.1 ± 1.9 for japonica type (see table). NPBP showed almost no differences between the two types. The ratio for NLVBFI/NPBP for 10 indicas averaged 1.97 and ranged from

1.64 to 2.27. The ratio for 10 japonicas averaged 1.13 and ranged from 1.02 to 1.19.

It seems that the ratio can be considered a new character to distinguish the two types. The difference in NLVBFI between the two types may relate to evolution and to nutrient transport. □

NLVBFI and NPBP^a in selected indica and japonica varieties. Hunan, China.

	NLVBFI		NPBP		A/B
	Average (A)	CV (%)	Average (B)	CV (%)	
<i>Indica</i>					
Guang-lu-ai 4	14.6	8.7	7.2	12.8	2.08
Yu-chi 231-8	15.5	8.7	8.0	8.8	1.94
Xiang-ai-zhao 9	18.1	6.1	8.2	15.0	2.21
Ke-zhen 145	27.5	9.1	16.0	5.6	1.69
Wei-you 6	24.1	16.0	12.0	5.6	2.01
Zhen-zhu-ai	22.7	13.6	11.4	9.4	1.99
Qui-chao 2	22.9	9.5	11.6	7.3	1.97
Qiang-yan 1811	18.7	8.7	9.6	11.1	1.95
Mi-yan 23	23.2	10.7	10.2	11.1	2.27
IR26	18.7	14.9	11.2	5.6	1.64
<i>Japonica</i>					
Tian-jin-yong	12.0	9.6	10.8	8.5	1.11
Long-hu 6	11.7	7.0	10.2	12.0	1.14
58 fu-nuo	8.3	9.9	7.0	19.0	1.18
177 fu-lei	10.7	15.7	10.5	14.3	1.02
6107	11.0	14.8	10.3	17.8	1.07
78-14	9.5	12.9	8.0	13.4	1.19
4001	10.3	20.9	9.2	25.2	1.12
Hai203	9.5	8.8	8.0	11.8	1.19
Yi-chang 105	11.6	10.8	10.6	15.4	1.09

^aMeans of 10 plants, including 5 main culms and 5 tillers. NLVBFI = large vascular bundles in first internode, NPBP = primary branches of panicle.

Grain quality and nutritional value

Correlation between rice grain and straw protein content and yield

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BR3 rice was grown at the Bangladesh Agricultural University Farm, Mymensingh, May-Oct 1982 with 4 treatments of ZnO (0, 2, 5, and 8 kg Zn/ha) and gypsum (0, 20,30, and 40